

GL MICAVE

D5.4 Open API and interoperability

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2020 GA No. 952908
Project title	Global Omic Data Integration on Animal, Vegetal and Environment Sectors
Duration of the project	1st November 2020 - 30th April 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP5: Big Data platform backend integration and data exploitation / Task 5.5: Open API and Interoperability
Document due Date:	31/10/2023 (M36)
Actual date of delivery	22/12/2023 (M38)
Leader of this deliverable	EUT
Type	Demo
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	30/11/2023	EUT	Draft version circulated to partners
0.2	20/12/2023	EUT	Elaborated document
0.3	20/12/2023	TREE	Revision from WPL
1.0	22/12/2023	EUT	Revision & Submission

Executive summary

This document outlines the task focused on establishing interoperable mechanisms to streamline access to digital services and orchestrate the entire GLOMICAVE platform. The primary objective is the orchestration of GLOMICAVE modules, encompassing the data lake, analytical services, and visualization components.

This report particularly emphasizes two pivotal aspects: the development of a Backend API for executing data processing services and a Backend API for data interaction using the Gremlin API with the Neptune Graph Database. These components will strengthen GLOMICAVE's ability to efficiently process data and foster comprehensive data interaction.

This strategic approach not only enhances GLOMICAVE's technical functionality but also contributes to its international standing. Key achievements are highlighted, challenges addressed, and guidelines for future implementations are provided, solidifying GLOMICAVE's role in genomics and research.

The following sections have been included:

- Section 1: information about the approach for the orchestration of modules (architecture and interaction)
- Section 2: description of Open API for Analytical Services
- Section 3: description of Open API for Data Querying
- Section 4: practical applications of Open API
- Section 5: conclusions and next steps

GLOMICAVE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 952908.

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List of abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
EC	European Commission
ECS	Elastic Container Service
EU	European Union
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
REST	Representational State Transfer
S3	Simple Storage Service
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The main purpose of the Task 5.5, titled “Open API and Interoperability” is to establish a cohesive and interoperable digital ecosystem for genomic data analysis. In a world where data plays a pivotal role in scientific advancements, this task addresses the critical need for seamless collaboration and efficient access to digital services within the GLOMICAVE platform.

At the heart of GLOMICAVE lies the integration of diverse modules, each contributing a unique set of functionalities—ranging from managing extensive genomic datasets in the data lake to conducting sophisticated analytical processes and providing intuitive data visualizations. Task 5.5 embarks on the crucial journey of orchestrating these modules to ensure their harmonious operation.

2 Orchestration of GLOMICAVE Modules

2.1 Micro-Services Architecture

To achieve intelligent and selective functionality, the task embraces a micro-services architecture, enhancing efficiency and introducing flexibility through a common service discovery mechanism. Design patterns are adopted to ensure that each component is invoked precisely when its services are required, optimizing the overall performance of the GLOMICAVE platform. The micro-services architecture is designed to distribute intelligence across different platform components, invoking each service selectively only when required, and incorporating design patterns for flexibility and a common service discovery mechanism.

The adoption of a Microservices Architecture within the AWS environment is a strategic decision aimed at optimizing the performance and scalability of GLOMICAVE. This section delves into the specifics of how AWS tools and services, such as AWS Lambda, AWS ECS (Elastic Container Service). The utilization of AWS resources ensures agility, responsiveness, and resource efficiency in the orchestration of GLOMICAVE.

Figure 1 GLOMICAVE architecture

2.2 Module Interaction

2.2.1 Use of REST APIs

In realizing the seamless interaction among GLOMICAVE modules, the Implementation of REST APIs serves as a key element. This intricate process involves the careful design and deployment of REST APIs, which act as the conduit for communication between various microservices within the architecture. RESTful principles, such as stateless communication and resource-based interactions, are harnessed to ensure standardized and efficient data exchange. This approach not only facilitates the integration of modules but also establishes a foundation for scalable and interoperable interactions.

Furthermore, the REST APIs are tailored to accommodate the specific needs of each module, providing a flexible and adaptive framework. By adhering to RESTful principles, GLOMICAVE achieves a level of abstraction that enhances modularity, allowing for the independent development and evolution of individual microservices. This implementation ensures that each module can efficiently communicate and share data, fostering a cohesive and agile ecosystem within the GLOMICAVE platform.

2.2.2 Intelligent Distribution of Interaction based on Service Needs

An integral facet of GLOMICAVE's microservices architecture lies in the intelligent distribution of interaction based on service needs. This sophisticated mechanism optimizes the allocation of

interactions between modules, taking into account the specific requirements and demands of each service. By dynamically managing the distribution of computational tasks, GLOMICAVE ensures a judicious use of resources, preventing unnecessary invocation of services and promoting an environment of resource efficiency.

The intelligent distribution mechanism is designed to adapt to varying workloads and service requests, maximizing responsiveness and overall system efficiency. This adaptive approach guarantees that computational intelligence is invoked selectively, aligning with the evolving needs of the platform. GLOMICAVE's commitment to intelligent interaction distribution enhances its capacity to handle diverse tasks, contributing to the scalability, robustness, and optimized performance of the microservices-based ecosystem.

3 Open API for Digital Analytical Services

Recognizing the significance of external accessibility, Task 5.5 undertakes the development of an Open API for digital analytical services. This API, structured under REST architecture, ensuring a scalable and modular approach to service exposure and interaction, and exposed through the Swagger tool, serves as a gateway for users to seamlessly interact with and leverage the analytical capabilities of GLOMICAVE.

Figure 2 Back-End API for executing data processing services

3.1 Swagger Tool for API Exposure

The Swagger Interface stands as a robust tool, playing a pivotal role in shaping the landscape of modern API development. It serves as a comprehensive framework, purpose-built to simplify and enhance the processes involved in building, documenting, and consuming APIs. Derived from the OpenAPI Specification, Swagger introduces a standardized approach to describing the GLOMICAVE API, offering a clear interface that simplifies API exposure, rendering it easily comprehensible and accessible.

The GLOMICAVE API is accessible through the following link: <http://glomicave-swagger-bucket.s3-website-eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/>. The accompanying image illustrates the endpoint through which users can execute analytical services, depicting both the methods and data models.

Figure 3 Swagger interface of Open API for Analytical Services (I)

In Figure 3, note that the endpoint **"/workflows/{workflowId}/run"** necessitates a parameter named **"workflowId"** for the request. Additionally, it provides insight into the structure of the HTTPS request body, which, in this instance, is presented in JSON format as follows:

```
{
  runId          string
  callbackUrl    string($uri)
}
```

Figure 4 Swagger interface of Open API for Analytical Services (II)

4 Open API for Data Querying

This section delves into the critical aspect of empowering data querying within the GLOMICAVE platform through the implementation of versatile endpoints. The establishment of versatile endpoints plays a pivotal role in facilitating seamless and efficient access to genomic data, enabling users to interact with the platform using various query languages. The strategic creation of these endpoints enhances the platform's adaptability, accommodating diverse user preferences and technical requirements for querying genomic information.

In essence, Task 5.5 is not merely a technical undertaking; the implementation of versatile endpoints ensures a seamless process for retrieving genomic data. Users can interact with the GLOMICAVE platform effortlessly, regardless of their familiarity with specific query languages. This approach democratizes access to genomic information, fostering collaboration among researchers, scientists, and experts who may have varied preferences in querying data.

4.1 Endpoint Customization

One key focus of this initiative is the customization of endpoints to support multiple query languages. By incorporating support for Gremlin, OpenCypher, and SPARQL, users gain the flexibility to employ their preferred query language, promoting a user-friendly and adaptable environment for data exploration and analysis.

Empowering data querying through versatile endpoints aligns with the broader goal of enhancing the user experience within the GLOMICAVE platform. Researchers and analysts can leverage their expertise in different query languages, promoting a collaborative and inclusive environment for genomic data exploration.

Figure 5 SPARQL API architecture for querying the Knowledge Graph as RDF Graph Database

4.2 Future Considerations

As the GLOMICAVE platform evolves, continual efforts will be invested in refining and expanding the range of versatile endpoints. This ensures that the platform remains at the forefront of accommodating emerging query languages and evolving user needs, providing a dynamic and forward-looking solution for genomic data querying.

The implementation of versatile endpoints serves as a cornerstone in empowering users to query genomic data efficiently, promoting inclusivity, and fostering a collaborative environment within the GLOMICAVE platform.

5 Practical Applications of the Open API

5.1 Data Visualization

One of the paramount applications of the GLOMICAVE Open API lies in its ability to seamlessly facilitate data visualization, providing users with a dynamic and interactive experience. Below, we illustrate a practical example of how to execute a query through the API and visualize the results in a graph format.

As a practical example, we utilized Jupyter Notebook to showcase the configuration file, providing insights into the data source. In this instance, GLOMICAVE operates in conjunction with Amazon Neptune, a purpose-built graph database service. Amazon Neptune exposes an endpoint and port, serving as the target for data retrieval. This endpoint and port combination acts as the entry point for accessing genomic data stored in the Amazon Neptune database.

```

%graph_notebook_config
{
  "host": "ontology-eurecat-cluster.cluster-cuf2qekfsvtk.eu-west-1.neptune.amazonaws.com",
  "neptune_service": "neptune-db",
  "port": 8182,
  "proxy_host": "",
  "proxy_port": 8182,
  "auth_mode": "DEFAULT",
  "load_from_s3_arn": "arn:aws:iam::772667446441:role/NeptuneLoaderRoleEURECAT",
  "ssl": true,
  "ssl_verify": true,
  "aws_region": "eu-west-1",
  "sparql": {
    "path": "sparql"
  },
  "gremlin": {
    "traversal_source": "g",
    "username": "",
    "password": "",
    "message_serializer": "graphsonv3"
  },
  "neo4j": {
    "username": "neo4j",
    "password": "password",
    "auth": true,
    "database": null
  }
}

```

Figure 6 Query Configuration

As we can see the config file aims to the API link `ontology-eurecat-cluster.cluster-cuf2qekfsvtk.eu-west-1.neptune.amazonaws.com` before to create and send the query.

As the API is prepared to admit queries to retrieve data in three different languages, as we mentioned before Gremlin, OpenCypher, and SPARQL.

Query Example:

Suppose we want to retrieve the metabolic pathways where hydrogen sulfide appears, as well as to identify the publications where synonyms of this same compound appear.

```

%%oc

MATCH (pw:PATHWAY)-[pwpart:IS_PART_OF_PATHWAY]-(n:NAMED_ENTITY)-
[has:HAS_LF]->(lf:LEXICAL_FORM)-[r:SYNONYM_WITH]-
(lf2:LEXICAL_FORM)-[apps:APPEARS_IN|APPEARS_IN_LOWERCASE]-
>(s:SENTENCE)-[ispart:IS_PART_OF_SENTENCE]->(p:PUBLICATION)

WHERE toLower(lf.uid)=toLower("h2s")

RETURN lf, lf2, r, s, p, pw, n, pwpart, has, ispart, apps

LIMIT 20

```

Figure 7 OpenCypher query example

The first line is to indicate the language we want to retrieve the data, in that case we indicate OpenCypher by writing this line “%%oc”, in case of Gremlin or SPARQL the line would be “%%gremlin” or “%%sparql”.

On one hand, in the first part of the query, it seeks the metabolic pathways in which hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) appears. On the other hand, in the second part of the query, it looks for sentences (and respective publications) where synonyms of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) appear. All nodes and relationships involved are displayed, limited to the first 20 sentences found.

Going into more detail on the relationships, it is sought that synonyms of the term "H₂S" can appear both in uppercase and lowercase within the sentences of the abstracts of the publications.

Data visualization:

The response from the Open API will include relevant genomic data, such as gene expression levels, mutations, or other related information. To enhance user understanding, this data can be efficiently visualized in graphical format.

By using a graph, users can visually interpret gene expression levels under different conditions or identify specific mutations at different positions. This graphical representation adds clarity and insight, empowering users to draw meaningful conclusions from genomic data.

Figure 8 Result of query represented in graph

The query result presents the requested information by visualizing Publications, Sentences, Lexical Forms, Pathways, Metabolites, and Relationships. This comprehensive view helps understand how the data is interconnected and provides context to the extracted knowledge.

As demonstrated, the Open API not only streamlines the efficient retrieval of genomic data but also empowers users to represent this data in visually comprehensible graphs. This feature encourages a more intuitive and informative exploration of genomic information within the GLOMICAVE platform.

6 Conclusions

In the current deliverable as part of the WP5 titled “Big Data platform backend integration and data exploitation frontend”, we demonstrate the implementation of the architecture for both Open APIs within the GLOMICAVE project—the API governing analytical services and the Open API for data querying.

To achieve this, we leverage a suite of tools within the AWS environment, optimizing project performance and scalability. The utilization of AWS resources ensures the agility, responsiveness, and resource efficiency necessary for orchestrating GLOMICAVE effectively.

The implementation of the Open APIs results in the creation of various endpoints tailored for different interpreters, facilitating data querying. This enhancement significantly improves the user experience, enabling users to query data using their preferred syntax. Moreover, it fosters collaboration within the GLOMICAVE ecosystem, providing a seamless and efficient means of interacting with genomic data.